

THE AZO COMPOUNDS FROM MORPHINE. PART I.

BY AMARESH CHANDRA ROY.

Morphine has been coupled with various diazotised amines to produce azo-dyestuffs. It has been found that the pharmacological activity of morphine becomes modified but is not destroyed.

The coupling of morphine with a diazonium salt to produce an azo-dyestuff was first studied by Wieland and Kappelmeir (*Annalen*, 1911, 383, 336), who prepared phenylazomorphine from diazobenzene chloride and a solution of morphine in alkali. Later on Lautenschlager (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1919, 287, 13) tried to prepare azo compounds of morphine, emetine, sparteine, physostigmine, piperidine, conine, and nicotine by coupling these alkaloids with diazotised arsenic acid, diazobenzenesulphonic acid, 2:5-dichlorobenzenediazonium chloride etc. in alkaline solution and found that morphine was the only alkaloid of opium which gave an azo-dye but the physiological action of the former was destroyed by its conversion into diazonium compound. Recently Charrier and Neri (*Gazzetta*, 1929, 59, 804) prepared 2-phenylazomorphine and studied its transformation into 2-phenyl-azoapomorphine by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid.

The present work is undertaken with a view to study the effect of substitution by diazo and substituted diazo groups on the pharmacological activity of morphine and also to prepare azo-dyestuffs showing optical activity.

The following aromatic amino compounds have been diazotised and coupled with morphine in alkaline solution and the corresponding azo-dyestuff obtained: aniline, *p*-toluidine, 2:4-xylydine, *p*-chloroaniline, 2:4:6-tribromoaniline, *p*-aminophenol, *o*-anisidine, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitroaniline, benzidine and α -naphthylamine. The azo compounds, thus prepared, are coloured substances of shades varying from orange-red to deep brown.

All these compounds show distinct hypnotic and analgesic action like morphine. They have practically no effect on paramoecia even in a concentration of 1 in 100 and are less toxic and less depressant than morphine. They have distinct action on the central nervous system but develop no convulsion and exaggeration of reflexes. The compounds have practically no action on the heart and in lower concentrations increase the tone and amplitude of contractions of the isolated intestine. Thus it appears that the pharmacological activity of morphine is not altogether destroyed, as was previously observed by Lautenschlager (*loc. cit.*).

The optical rotatory properties could not be determined owing to the intense colour of the compounds in caustic alkalis. Concentrated solutions of the compounds in alcohol and other solvents were also tried but no appreciable rotation could be observed owing probably to the small concentration of the azo-dyes in the solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenylazomorphine.—Diazobenzene chloride, prepared from aniline (4.6 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (23 g.) and sodium nitrite (3.5 g.), was gradually added, during the course of half an hour, with constant stirring to a freshly prepared cooled solution of morphine (15 g.) in sodium hydroxide. The dark red liquid was allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature, filtered from the resinous matter and on neutralisation with dilute hydrochloric acid, gave a brown amorphous powder which was filtered and washed with water. The compound, thus obtained, was redissolved in *N*-sodium hydroxide and reprecipitated by neutralising with *N*-hydrochloric acid; this process was repeated twice and the precipitate was ultimately filtered, washed with water and dried in a steam-oven. From dilute ethyl alcohol it crystallised in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 175° (decomp.), and was identical with 2-phenylazomorphine, prepared by Wieland and Kappelmeier (*loc. cit.*).

All other compounds were prepared in the same way as the phenylazomorphine by taking equimolecular quantities of the amino compounds and morphine. For the final purification, the compounds were dissolved in anhydrous methyl alcohol, the solution clarified with animal charcoal, filtered and was concentrated; the dystuffs were reprecipitated from this solution by adding an excess of ether, filtered and dried. The results are summarised in Table I.

With the exception of phenylazomorphine, which crystallises from ethyl alcohol in orange-yellow needles, all other compounds are amorphous powders which do not crystallise from any solvent. The yield of the crude products in all cases is 30-35% of that required by theory because of resin formations. All these compounds are sparingly soluble in water, petroleum ether, ether and chloroform but soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, glacial acetic acid and pyridine. They are slightly soluble in concentrated ammonia but dissolve freely in dilute alkali hydroxide from which they can be precipitated by neutralisation with dilute mineral acids or by passing a current of carbon dioxide. In dilute mineral acids all of them dissolve, though sparingly, with an orange-yellow colour. They

TABLE I.

(M stands for the azomorphine group $C_{11}H_{16}O_3-N-N=N-$ in the formulæ).

Name of the compound.	Formula.	Appearance on purification.	M. p.	Colour in conc. H_2SO_4 .	Colour in NaOH.	Colour in Erdmann's reagent.	Colour with Froede's reagent.	Analysis. Found.	Calc.
Phenylazo-morphine	$M-C_6H_5$	Orange-yellow needles	175° (decomp.)	Red	Deep red	Brown	Red	N, 10.51	10.79
<i>p</i> -Tolylazo-morphine	$M-C_6H_4-CH_3$	Orange amorphous powder	210° (decomp.)	"	"	"	"	N, 10.08 C, 70.98 H, 5.9	10.42 71.46 6.1
2 : 4-Dimethylphenylazo-morphine	$M-C_6H_3(CH_3)_2$	Orange-red powder	Does not fuse at 300°	"	"	"	Blood-red	N, 9.67 C, 71.60 H, 6.2	10.07 71.94 6.47
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4-Cl$	Maroon-red powder	"	"	"	Yellow changing to brown	Chocolate	N, 9.48	9.91
2 : 4 : 6-Tribromophenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_2Br_3$	Deep red powder	"	Dark red	"	"	Deep "	N, 5.3	6.71
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4OH$	Dark brown powder	"	Dirty pink	Reddish brown	Reddish brown	Dirty pink	N, 9.92	10.37
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4-OCH_3$	Chocolate powder	"	"	Orange	Deep brown	Pink changing to red	N, 9.85	10.02
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4-NO_2$	Light brown powder	"	Brown	Bright red	Brown changing to yellow	Brown changing to yellow	N, 9.35 C, 63.15 H, 4.93	9.67 63.59 5.07
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4-NO_2$	Dark brown powder	"	Yellowish brown	Blood-red	Orange	"	N, 9.28	9.67
<i>p</i> -Nitro phenylazomorphine	$M-C_6H_4-NO_2$	"	"	Brown	Red	Orange	Deep brown	N, 9.41	9.67
Resazinic-tetrazo-morphine	$M-C_6H_4-C_6H_4-M$	Dark chocolate powder	"	Magenta	Deep red	Brown changing to orange	Violet-red	N, 10.67	10.82
α Naphthylazomorphine	$M-C_{10}H_7$	Reddish brown powder	"	Violet	"	"	Violet	N, 9.64	9.56

dissolve in cold concentrated sulphuric acid giving deeply coloured solutions of varying shades, depending upon the nature of the substituents, which become yellow on dilution with water giving precipitates of the original dyestuff, but a prolonged treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid at the ordinary temperature changes them probably into apo-compounds (*cf.* Charrier and Neri, *loc. cit.*). The hydrochloric acid solutions of the compounds give with a solution of ferric chloride greenish yellow colouration which changed to deep yellow on boiling in all cases. With concentrated nitric acid all these compounds give yellow colourations which become almost colourless on warming owing to decomposition. They do not reduce ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and give colour reactions entirely different from morphine with Eirdmann's and Froede's reagents. For the pharmacological work the compounds are dissolved in the minimum amount of sodium hydroxide and the sodium salts, thus formed, are precipitated with an excess of alcohol, filtered dried and used for the investigation.

Further work on the pharmacological action of these compounds is in progress.

My best thanks are due to Dr. P. C. Ray, Professor of Pharmacology, Prince of Wales Medical College, Patna, for giving me facilities to work in his laboratory.

B. N. COLLEGE, PATNA.

Received April 27, 1940.
